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A Note on The Development of Hindu Mathematics in India

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Abstract:

A galaxy to Mathematicians and Astronomers flourished in Indian Mathematics subcontinent during the classical period from 400 AD to 1200 AD. The important contributions were made by Indian scholars like Aryabhata (476-550 AD), Varahamihira (b.505 AD), Brahmagupta (598-669 AD), Bhaskara I (b.525 AD), Mahaviracarya (c.850 AD), Sridharacarya (c.850 AD), Aryabhata II (c.950 AD) and Bhaskara II (1114-1185 AD) are some of them who contributed much the development of Hindu Mathematics.

These great scholar of Mathematical Sciences enriched the knowledge of the decimal number system, negative number, Arithmetic, Algebra, Astronomy, Geometry (Plane and spherical), Trigonometry and even differential calculus.

The Indian Mathematicians made early contribution to the study of the concept of zero as a number. The modern definitions of sine and cosine were developed in India. These Mathematical concepts were transmitted to the Middle East, China and Europe and led to further developments that now form the foundations of many areas of Mathematics. A later landmark in Indian Mathematics was development of the series expansion for trigonometric function (sine, cosine and arc tangent) by Mathematicians of the Kerla school in the 15th century AD.

In the present paper, we have made effort to high-light some salient features of the Mathematical Sciences and its various application made by the development of Hindu Mathematics for the benefit of our new generation.

Keywords: Subcontinent, Mathematical concepts, Astronomy, Mental Arithmetic, Determination, Bija-Ganita, Decimal place-value, Quadratic Equation, Trapezium, Indeterminate Equation, Squaring and Cubing, Rule of Three, Trisatika, Notation Value, Permutations and Combinations.

Introduction:

The Hindu contributions in Mathematics are significant. A study of Mathematical Sciences including Astronomy, Geometry and Algebra flourished well in Asian countries mainly in India, China and Arabian Peninsula. Within this period a number of Mathematicians and Astronomers. It is worth mentioning here that Indian Astronomy is the oldest of all the Sciences of the human race.

Ganita literally means “the Science of calculation” and is the Hindu name for Mathematics. The term is a very ancient one and occurs copiously in vedic literature. The Vedanga Jyotisa gives in the highest place of honour among the Sciences which form the Vedanga:

यथा शिखा मयूराणां नागानां मणयो यथा ।
तद्वद् वेदांगशास्त्राणां गणितं मूर्ध्नि स्थितम् ॥ (Vedanga Jyotisa, verse-35)

“As the crests on the heads of peacocks, as the gems on the hoods of snakes, so is Mathematics (Ganita) at the top of the Sciences and the head of all knowledge.”

It is believed that some time before the beginning of the Christian era, there was renaissance of Hindu Mathematics. Astronomy became a separate subject and Geometry came to be included within its scope. The Hindu Mathematics of the early renaissance period consisted of the following :

1. Parikarma (fundamental operations)
2. Vyavahara (determinations)
3. Rajju (rope, meaning Geometry)
4. Rasi (rule of three)
5. Kalasavarna (operations with fractions)
6. Yavat tavat (as many as, meaning simple equations)
7. Varga (square, meaning quadratic equations)
8. Ghana (cube, meaning cubic equations)
9. Varga- Varga (biquadratic equations)
10. Vikalpa (permutations and combinations)

Thus Ganita came to mean Mathematics in general, while “finger arithmetic” as well as “mental arithmetic” were excluded from the scope of its meaning. For the calculations involved in Ganita, the use of some writing material was essential. The calculations were performed on a board (pati). Thus the term ‘Patiganita’ or ‘Dhuli-karma’ came to be used for higher Mathematics. Later on the section of Ganita dealing with Algebra was given the name of Bija-ganita. The first to effort this separation was Brahmagupta (628 AD), but he did not use the term Bija-ganita. The chapter dealing with algebra in his Brahma-Sphuta-Siddhanta is called Kuttaka. Sridharacarya (750 AD) regarded Patiganita and Bija-ganita as separate and wrote separate treatises on each. This distinction between Patiganita and Bija-ganita has been preserved by later writers.

A study in the origin and development of Mathematics shows that nothing surpasses in importance invasion of zero we take pride in the fact that our ancestors gave shape to this zero and used it in diverse manners and brought phenomenal change in the field of Mathematics as discipline. The vivid use of zero and decimal place-value system of numeration is found in the Indian Mathematical work from 500 BC to 600 AD.

The first use of the word 'place' for the denomination is met with in the Jaina canonical work 'Anuyogadvara-sutra' (c.100 BC) in the total number of human beings in the world is given as : "a number which when expressed in terms of denominations, koti-koti, etc., occupies 29 places (29 sthana) or it is beyond the 24th place and within the 32nd place or it is a number obtained by multiplying sixth square (of two) by (its) fifth square (i.e., 2^{96})".

A system of expressing numbers by means of words arranged as in the place-value notation was developed and perfected in India in the early centuries of the Christian era. The system is used in works on Astronomy, Mathematics and metrics, as well as in the dates of inscriptions and in manuscripts. The words denoting the numbers from one to nine and zero, with the use of the principle of place-value, give us a very convenient method of expressing numbers by word chronograms. For example, the number 1230 may be expressed in many ways :

1. kha-guna-kara-adi,
2. kha-loka-karna-candra,
3. akasa-kala-netra-dhara, etc.

The earliest instance of the use of the word numerals with place-value in its current form is found in the "Agni-Purana". Bhattotpala in his commentary on the Brihat-Samhita has given a quotation for "Paulisa-Siddhanta" (c.400) in which the word system is used. The number expressed in this quotation is kha(0) Kha (0) asta(8) muni(7) rama(3) asvi(2) netra(2) asta(8) sara(5) ratripah(1) = 1,582,237,800.

Later Astronomical and Mathematical works such as the Surya-Siddhanta (c.300), the Pancha-Siddhantika (c.505), the Maha and Laghu-bhaskariya (c.522), the Brahma-sphuta- siddhanta (c.628), the Trisatika (c.750) and Ganita-sara-sangraha (c.850), all make use of the word notation.

Tradition places Aryabhata I (born 476 AD) at the head of Indian Mathematicians. His Mathematical rules are given in Gitikapada. In his Gitikapada, he introduces the alphabetical system and decimal number, tables of Astronomical constants. Trigonometrical sine and other numerical data are given, along with rules for the extraction of square and cube roots, areas of triangles, trapezium, volume

of pyramid and sphere, value of π , arithmetical progression, summation of series, interest, rule of three, fractions, method of constructing sine tables and indeterminate equations of the first degree.

Varāhamihira (b.505 AD), son of Adityadasa of Kapitthaka wrote the famous Pancha-Siddhantika and Brihat-Samhita. His most important contribution is the preparation of the corrected version of the Indian calendar with the warning for the future that the calendar should be periodically corrected by taking into account the accumulated precision.

Brahmagupta (b.598 AD), who wrote his Brahma-Sphuta- Siddhanta in his 13th year. Brahmagupta called the 12th chapter as Ganita and the 18th chapter as Kuttaka. The Abbasid Khalif-al-Mansur (712-775 AD) of Baghdad got Brahma-Sphuta-Siddhanta translated in Arabic in 770 AD with the help of Kanka of Ujjain. Brahmagupta also obtained the solution of the indeterminate equation.

$$Nx^2 + 1 = y^2$$

Mahaviracharya, the most celebrated Jaina Mathematician of the 9th century wrote Ganita-Sara-Sangraha in 850 AD, which contained mostly pure Mathematics, giving operations with numbers, squaring and cubing, square roots and cube roots, summation of arithmetic and geometric series, fractions, rule of three, mensuration and algebra.

He was also the first Mathematician to give the formula:

$${}^nC_r = \frac{n(n-1)(n-2)\dots\dots\dots(n-r+1)}{1,2,3,\dots\dots\dots, r}$$

on permutations and combinations.

The next great Hindu Mathematician of the period was Sridharacarya who flourished about (750 AD). Sridharacarya wrote his Trisatika, the method given in which division by means of factors, reached Italy, in the middle ages via Arbia and was named as “Modo Pardiego”. He made many discoveries in Algebra, Arithmetic and Mensuration. He wrote his famous text “Patiganita” which contains Arithmetic, Mensuration, Geometry and Algebra.

The great Mathematician Bhaskara I (c.522 AD) wrote two text on Mathematical Sciences entitled Maha-Bhaskariya and Laghu-Bhaskariya. In his text Bhaskara I used the terms Kutta for the first time for indeterminate equation of the first degree.

In Bhaskara's Lilavati we have Arithmetic, Algebra, Geometry, Mensuration and a bit of Trigonometry. If we go through it carefully, we realize how close to reality was the study of Mathematics in those days. Problems written in beautiful, lucid and simple shlokas have, in addition to their Mathematical value, their literary value as well. I cannot resist the temptation of citing at least of them by way of illustration:

चक्रक्रौञ्चाकुलितसलिले क्वापि दृष्टं तडागे
तोयादूर्ध्वं कमलकलिकाग्रं वितस्तिप्रमाणम् ।
मन्दं मन्दं चलितमनिलेनाहतं हस्तयुग्मे
तस्मिन् मग्नं गणक कथय क्षिप्रमम्भः प्रमाणम् ॥ (लीलावती, क्षेत्र-व्यवहार)

i.e. we saw a pond full of water and birds, like chakar and krauncha, in which the top of a lotus bud, on span in length, was visible above water. Soft blowing breeze drowned it in water at a distance of two hands (four spans). O calculator, Please tell quickly the depth of water in the period.

According to the question, we have

$$h - p = \frac{1}{2}, b = 2.$$

We know that, $h^2 - p^2 = b^2$

$$\text{or, } (h + p)(h - p) = b^2$$

$$\text{or, } (h + p) \times \frac{1}{2} = 2^2$$

$$\text{or, } h + p = 4 \times 2 = 8$$

$$\text{Thus, } h = \frac{1}{2} \left(8 + \frac{1}{2} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{17}{2} = \frac{17}{4}$$

$$\text{And } p = \frac{1}{2} \left(8 - \frac{1}{2} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{15}{2} = \frac{15}{4}$$

Further Sripati, Manjulacarya, Jinabhadra, Vatesvara, Satananda & Padmanabha contributed much to the development of Hindu Mathematics.

Conclusion:

From the above facts it is a well established that knowledge of Mathematical Sciences including the concept of numerals words, numeral symbol, zero, decimal value, place-value, Arithmetic, Astronomy, Geometry, Algebra & Notation value finds there origin in the soil of India. Certainly, ancient and medieval India has enlightened the whole world as a whole but the development of Hindu Mathematics during 4th to 12th century AD.

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